

SUBUNIT-DEPENDENT INTERACTION OF PROPOXAZEPAM AND ITS METABOLITE WITH THE γ -AMINO BUTYRIC ACID TYPE A RECEPTOR

Anatoliy Reder
SLC "InterChem"

86 Lyustdorfskaya road, Odessa, Ukraine, 65080

Vitalii Larionov ¹✉
vitaliy.larionov@gmail.com

Mykola Golovenko ¹

¹Laboratory of Physical-Chemical Pharmacology
A. V. Bogatsky Physico-Chemical Institute of NAS of Ukraine
86 Lyustdorfskaya road, Odessa, Ukraine, 65080

✉Corresponding author

Abstract

Benzodiazepines (BDZ) are widely used in clinics in the treatment of psychiatric disorders, and their main action is considered to be determined by more selective binding with $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$ or $\alpha 5$ subunits of GABA receptor.

The aim of this work was studying of the molecular mechanism of action of new analgesic – propoxazepam and its metabolite (3-hydroxypropoxazepam) on $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$ subunits containing GABA_A channels.

Materials and methods GABA $\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 2\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 3\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 4\beta 3\gamma 2$ and $\alpha 5\beta 3\gamma 2$ ionotropic GABA_ARs expressed in HEK293 were used on the automated SP384PE Patch Clamp system. In addition, Propoxazepam, 3-hydroxypropoxazepam, diazepam (positive allosteric modulator) and GABA (positive control) were administered at concentrations 0.001–300 nM to determine the EC₅₀ and E_{max} for corresponding substances.

Results The α subunit plays a significant role in determining the receptor's affinity for propoxazepam and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam. The rank order of decreasing EC₅₀ are $\alpha 1 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 3 > \alpha 4$ (propoxazepam) and $\alpha 1 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 3 > \alpha 4$ (3-hydroxypropoxazepam), and for E_{max} $\alpha 3 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 1 > \alpha 4$ (propoxazepam), $\alpha 3 > \alpha 1 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 4$ (3-hydroxypropoxazepam).

The data, transformed to E_{max}/EC₅₀, show that propoxazepam exhibits tenfold (compared to diazepam) activity (taking into account the magnitude of the maximum effect) to the $\alpha 3$ subunit, which distinguishes it from 3-hydroxypropoxazepam.

Conclusion Due to the determined selectivity of propoxazepam for binding with different α subunit-containing GABA_A-receptors (mostly $\alpha 3$ and $\alpha 2$ types), it has the potential to provide analgesia with less sedation than non-selective BDZ.

Keywords: benzodiazepines, propoxazepam, 3-hydroxypropoxazepam, analgesic action, side effect, GABA receptor, α -subunits, expressed receptor, hyperpolarization, maximum effect.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5679.2022.002649

1. Introduction

Gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) is the major inhibitory neurotransmitter in the mammalian central nervous system, mediating its effects via activating GABA_A receptors (GABA_ARs). The GABA_ARs are multimember proteins, composed of five subunits ($\alpha 1$ -6, $\beta 1$ -3, $\gamma 1$ -3, δ , ϵ , θ , π) [1] and are the target of a range of compounds, including GABA agonists and antagonists, benzodiazepines (BDZ), neurosteroids, ethanol, various channel blockers, barbiturates [1, 2]. BDZ has found widespread clinical use, notably in the treatment of anxiety and sleep disorders and they are generally regarded as non-selective full agonists (positive allosteric modulators) since they generally activate to a similar degree GABA_ARs containing an $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$ or $\alpha 5$ subunit in combination with a βx and a $\gamma 2$ subunit. However, BDZ should be regarded as subtype-selective agents since they generally show no affinity for GABA_ARs containing an $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 6$ subunit [3]. Despite this selectivity, BDZ has adverse effects, including sedation, muscle relaxation, anterograde amnesia, ethanol

interaction, and abuse/dependence liability. However, it should not be overlooked that the former three side effects are of benefit in specific clinical contexts or patient populations [4].

An innovative compound created at our institute – propoxazepam, 7-Bromo-5(o-chlorophenyl)-3-propoxy-1,2-dihydro-3H-1,4-benzodiazepine-2-one is characterized by anticonvulsant [5], analgesic [6] and anti-inflammatory [7] action. We proved [8] that the mechanisms of the analgesic effect of propoxazepam involve the dopaminergic system, NMDA receptors, alpha-1 adrenoreceptors, and GABA_ARs. Regarding the mechanism of the anticonvulsant action of propoxazepam, it is due to its interaction with GABA- and glycine receptors [9, 10]. Therefore, the compound is considered a promising drug and undergoes the necessary clinical trials in Ukraine.

The aim of this work was studying of the molecular mechanism of action of new analgesic – propoxazepam and its metabolite (3-hydroxypropoxazepam) on $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$ subunits containing GABA_A channels.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Test substances

The test substances were evaluated in an 8-point concentration-response format (4 replicate wells/concentration). Substances were dissolved and initially diluted in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The final dilution was made in an extracellular solution. The final DMSO concentration in the assay was 0.6 % (v/v)

2.2. Positive Control Treatment Groups

Stock solutions of positive control articles were prepared in batches, aliquoted for individual use, stored frozen, and used within six months. The positive control test solutions were prepared fresh daily. The final DMSO concentration was 0.6 % (v/v). GABA_ARs agonist, GABA, was used as a positive control agonist. The GABA_ARs positive allosteric modulator (PAM) diazepam was used as a positive control PAM at $\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$ GABA_ARs.

2.3. Test Systems and Test Platform

In work were used the GABA $\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 2\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 3\beta 3\gamma 2$, $\alpha 4\beta 3\gamma 2$ and $\alpha 5\beta 3\gamma 2$ ionotropic GABA_ARs expressed in HEK293 (Human Embryonic Kidney 293) cells. Further, the corresponding receptors denoted as $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$, as having the similar β and γ subunits.

Electrophysiological experiments were performed using an automated SP384PE Patch Clamp (Syncropatch SP384PE) system in the Charles River Laboratories (Cleveland).

2.4. Compounds and solutions

The GABA_ARs agonist, GABA, 5 μ M (Sigma-Aldrich), was used as a positive control agonist. The GABA_ARs positive allosteric modulator (PAM), diazepam (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as a positive control PAM at $\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$ GABA_A receptors. Propoxazepam and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam (major metabolite) were synthesized according to the method described in [11]. The structure of the substance was determined and approved by a complex of physicochemical methods (IR and mass spectroscopy, as well as X-ray diffraction analysis). Chemical purity was confirmed by elemental analysis (99 %). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as a solvent for propoxazepam and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam (final concentrations 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, 10, 30, 100, 300 nM), and diazepam (0.001, 0.003, 0.01, 0.03, 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3 μ M). The extracellular solution was the final dilution. The DMSO concentration in the final solutions was 0.6 % (v/v).

2.5. Electrophysiological Procedures

Intracellular solution (mM): CsCl – 50 mM; CsF – 90 mM; MgCl₂ – 5 mM; EGTA – 1 mM; HEPES – 10 mM; *pH* adjusted to 7.2 with CsOH. In preparation for a recording session, the intracellular solution was loaded into the intracellular compartment of the population patch clamp (PPC) planar electrode. Extracellular solution HB-PS: NaCl, 137 mM; KCl, 4.0 mM; CaCl₂, 3.8 mM; MgCl₂ mM, 1; HEPES, 10 mM; Glucose, 10 mM; *pH* adjusted to 7.4. Holding potential: 70 mV.

Experimental procedures

PPC plate wells were filled (11 μL per well) with extracellular buffer. The cell suspension was put into the wells (9 μL per well) of the PPC planar electrode. Whole-cell recording configurations were established via patch perforation with currents recorded by onboard patch clamp amplifiers. The recording (scans) was performed twice: the first scan during the first application of the test article to detect agonist effects and a second scan two minutes after the test article co-application with 5 μM GABA to detect PAM effects.

Effects will be calculated based on peak current amplitudes measurements.

Statistical analyses

The data were plotted against achieved concentrations, and the concentration-response curve (where the response is expressed as % of the current in an experiment to control value) was fitted with the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Current} = Bck + \frac{Max - Bck}{1 + 10^{C_{50} + nC_x}}$$

Where C_x is the logarithm of test item concentration, n is the Hill coefficient, Max and Bck are the top and bottom plateau, and C_{50} is the logarithm of test item concentration at the curve turning point (mid-point between the top and bottom values). The C_{50} value, which is defined as the concentration at which the current corresponds to 50 % (after vehicle correction) of the maximum reached value, will be calculated from the above equation after the variables have been obtained from the fitting procedure.

Statistical analysis may be performed using an unpaired, 2-tailed Student's t-test. The null hypothesis (that no difference exists between test item and vehicle groups) was rejected when $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

In this study, the reference PAM, diazepam, showed a strong PAM effect with stimulation of the $\alpha 1\beta\gamma 2$ GABA_A-Rs in the presence of 5 μM GABA ($EC_{50\text{PAM}} = 0.017 \mu\text{M}$ and efficacy $\sim 300\%$, **Table 1, 2**). Diazepam was used as a reference substance for only $\alpha 1$ subunit-containing receptors since the demonstration of its high affinity to this isoform [12].

Propoxazepam was examined after stimulation of receptors in the presence of 5 μM GABA. **Table 1** shows a data summary for PAM effects.

Table 1

Effect of propoxazepam on GABA_A receptors, containing different α -subunits. Currents were normalized to the current elicited by 5 μM GABA at the lowest concentration of propoxazepam.

Conc., μM	$\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$	$\alpha 2\beta 3\gamma 2$	$\alpha 3\beta 3\gamma 2$	$\alpha 4\beta 3\gamma 2$	$\alpha 5\beta 3\gamma 2$	Diazepam	
						Conc., μM	$\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$
0.0001	100.00 \pm 13.42	100.00 \pm 25.30	100.00 \pm 18.08	100.00 \pm 16.26	100.00 \pm 10.97	0.001	100.00 \pm 18.20
0.0003	82.29 \pm 5.40	116.74 \pm 9.22	136.58 \pm 23.20	67.90 \pm 9.43	114.45 \pm 13.72	0.003	123.11 \pm 12.66
0.001	86.37 \pm 12.06	95.34 \pm 9.43	106.82 \pm 15.72	98.28 \pm 23.33	110.58 \pm 15.81	0.01	106.29 \pm 11.22
0.003	83.04 \pm 9.38	131.06 \pm 21.90	107.06 \pm 12.77	123.23 \pm 24.87	123.58 \pm 6.68	0.03	133.81 \pm 8.78
0.01	118.31 \pm 17.31	131.76 \pm 18.83	108.08 \pm 22.28	121.12 \pm 14.17	133.85 \pm 18.63	0.10	172.03 \pm 16.50
0.03	88.08 \pm 7.59	160.62 \pm 16.43	107.24 \pm 16.12	84.60 \pm 14.35	139.80 \pm 12.30	0.30	152.72 \pm 17.53
0.10	179.57 \pm 15.77	235.42 \pm 32.77	285.58 \pm 30.85	129.12 \pm 26.97	199.81 \pm 29.38	1.00	181.66 \pm 12.09
0.30	164.92 \pm 13.96	280.10 \pm 31.42	455.12 \pm 64.94	82.36 \pm 13.06	186.28 \pm 15.78	3.00	171.34 \pm 21.32
E_{MIN} (%)	82.3	95.3	100.0	67.9	100.0		100.0
E_{MAX} (%)	179.6	280.1	455.1	129.1	199.8		181.7
EC_{50} (μM)	0.018	0.038	0.098	> 0.3	0.02		0.04
Hillslope	-1.00	-1.11	-4.03	NC ^a	-0.81		-0.81

Note: a – NC – not calculated

Propoxazepam metabolite 3-hydroxypropoxazepam (**Table 2**) produced a powerful PAM effect at all GABA_ARs receptors (except for the $\alpha 4$) with $EC_{50\text{PAM}}$ potency in the nanomolar range from 2 to 17 nM and efficacy in the range from 240 % up to 400 %.

Table 2

Effect of 3-hydroxypropoxazepam on GABA_A receptors, containing different α -subunits. Currents were normalized to current elicited by 5 μ M GABA at the lowest concentration of 3-hydroxypropoxazepam.

Conc., μ M	$\alpha 1\beta 3g2$	$\alpha 2\beta 3g2$	$\alpha 3\beta 3g2$	$\alpha 4\beta 3g2$	$\alpha 5\beta 3g2$	Diazepam	
						Conc., μ M	$\alpha 1\beta 3g2$
0.0001	100.00±23.50	100.00±12.64	100.00±15.68	100.00±21.61	100.00±16.28	0.001	100.00±23.15
0.0003	103.37±13.79	123.63±20.17	130.14±22.88	82.36±18.92	112.64±27.21	0.003	148.71±30.31
0.001	183.24±25.72	163.14±20.94	87.30±7.52	81.70±14.51	130.47±15.73	0.01	188.11±20.73
0.003	290.55±46.08	217.10±28.73	170.58±28.97	92.44±16.77	111.50±20.12	0.03	203.23±42.95
0.01	277.76±48.68	298.89±55.48	210.37±57.70	80.59±19.35	159.12±25.10	0.10	296.94±59.89
0.03	352.65±56.24	336.68±21.77	302.44±65.33	92.52±19.56	210.69±12.85	0.30	306.45±49.48
0.10	355.31±38.98	266.46±45.25	381.40±65.30	91.44±24.45	240.17±27.64	1.00	263.59±53.85
0.30	312.37±56.39	342.19±31.42	425.76±57.63	63.00±15.23	186.59±32.64	3.00	256.06±20.28
E _{MIN} (%)	100.0	100.0	100.0	63.0	100.0		100.0
E _{MAX} (%)	355.3	342.2	425.8	100.0	240.2		306.4
EC ₅₀ (μ M)	0.002	0.003	0.017	> 0.3	0.01		0.017
Hillslope	1.00	0.98	1.03	NC ^a	0.90		0.85

Note: a – NC – not calculated

To eliminate the influence of the systematic component of variability in different experiments, a ratio normalized to similar values for the reference drug should be used (Table 3).

Table 3

Calculated normalized indicators of the studied compounds to different receptor subtypes concerning the reference drug (diazepam).

Receptor subtype	Propoxazepam	3-Hydroxypropoxazepam
$\alpha 1$	0.54	0.15
$\alpha 2$	2.15	0.21
$\alpha 3$	10.65	1.58
$\alpha 4$	–	–
$\alpha 5$	0.61	0.40
$\alpha 1\beta 3g2$ (diazepam)	1.00	1.00

4. Discussion

Metabolism (biochemical transformation) is an essential biological process that converts xenobiotics, including medicines, to water-soluble substances and eliminates toxic compounds from the body. As a result of the metabolism process, the parent compound can be converted to more (activation) or less (deactivation) active [13]. According to the results of previous studies [14], Propoxazepam metabolism leads to the formation of at least 3-hydroxyderivative, oxidized and dealkylated metabolites. The proportions of unchanged parent drug after 4-hour incubation with hepatocytes rat, dog, monkey and minipig varied between 37.1 to 96.0 % of the total peak response. The most abundant metabolite observed across all species was 3-hydroxypropoxazepam which accounted for between 2.5 to 46.5 % of the total peak response in the 4-hour samples. Four other minor metabolites were observed, representing <10 % of the total peak response. Therefore, the substances propoxazepam and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam were used in our studies.

In order to determine the biotarget with which compounds interact, we conducted [10] radioreceptor studies. It demonstrated that a value of the K_i in inhibition of specific binding of [³H]

flumazenil with synaptic membranes from the rat brain by propoxazepam is, on average, 3.5 ± 0.3 nM and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam 1,8 nM. Compared with the respective values for other BDZ, it is a rather significant value. In particular, the analogous indices for diazepam, chlordiazepoxide, nitrazepam, and oxazepam are 6.3, 220, 6.4, and 14.0, respectively [15]. Estimation of the integral activity of the compound is a rather important moment in our study. This index can be estimated according to the value of a GABA shift in the graph of displacement of the radioligand by the examined ligand in the absence and presence of 10^{-4} M GABA. The respective calculations showed that the GABA shift for propoxazepam is equal to 1.9. This fact allows us to consider the examined compound as a full agonist of GABA_ARs. The corresponding indices for such full agonists of the receptor as mentioned above as diazepam and flunitrazepam are equal to 2.89 and 2.73, respectively.

Some binding sites were determined using the molecular docking method on the selected GABA_ARs part [16] with complex formation energy from -78.64 to -85.29 kcal/mole. The total binding energy of the most numerous propoxazepam conformers cluster and GABA_ARs is similar. However, the contribution of Van-der-Vaal interactions and hydrogen bonds are not equal for different conformers. The main contribution in the complex formation makes polar amino acids residues (serine, asparagine, methionine and arginine – polar binding subcenter). However, for some conformers, the significant contribution has aromatic amino acids, mainly phenylalanine (Phe-31, Ala-135 – hydrophobic binding subcenter). Selectivity of a ligand for a specific GABA_ARs subtype can be obtained either by binding or efficacy by eliciting a biological response after binding to the receptor. Since binding experiments cannot reveal the complete potency profile of a ligand, subtype selectivity is also assessed in electrophysiological experiments performed with human embryonic kidney 293 cells.

In this study, we defined the impact of different GABA_ARs isoforms on the interaction with propoxazepam and its main metabolite, which allows us to expand our understanding of the action mechanism of the parent compound. For this, ionotropic GABA_A isoforms ($\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 4$ та $\alpha 5$) expressed in the HEK293 cells were used.

The electric activity of GABA_ARs can be understood with a series of parameters that describe and explain their responses to the various patterns of agonist exposure. We used so-called functional parameters (half-maximum effective concentration, EC_{50} ; Hill slope, n ; minimum effect, E_{min} (in comparison to background effect of the receptor at $5 \mu\text{M}$ GABA) and maximum reached effect, E_{max}), which describe respectively the current time-course and its dependence on agonist concentration.

The agonist effect of propoxazepam was examined during the first application at 2X concentrations (0.2 to 600 nM) (**Table 1**). Propoxazepam did not produce a significant, concentration-dependent activation of the GABA_ARs. It is expected that GABA_ARs antagonists inhibit currents elicited by $5 \mu\text{M}$ GABA. Propoxazepam did not produce a significant, concentration-dependent inhibition of the GABA_ARs, but the potent PAM effect at all GABA_ARs (except for the $\alpha 4$) with $EC_{50\text{PAM}}$ potency in the nanomolar range from 18 to 98 nM and efficacy in the range from 180 % up to 460 %. Propoxazepam showed no significant agonist or antagonist effects in all GABA_ARs subtypes tested. However, Propoxazepam did show robust PAM activity with $EC_{50\text{PAM}}$ in the nanomolar (18-100 nM) range at near-threshold GABA stimulation of the GABA_ARs. 3-Hydroxypropoxazepam had a pronounced effect at all GABA_ARs receptors (except the $\alpha 4$) with $EC_{50\text{PAM}}$ potency in the nanomolar range from 2 to 17 nM (**Table 2**).

It is known that the stereotypical PAM, diazepam, acts at near-threshold stimulation of GABA_ARs with GABA, and the magnitude of the PAM effect decreases after increasing concentrations of GABA. Agents acting on GABA_ARs have therapeutic use as anxiolytics, anticonvulsants, sedative-hypnotics and anaesthetics. These drugs increase GABA-mediated synaptic inhibition by directly activating GABA_ARs or, more usually, by enhancing the action of GABA on GABA_ARs. This latter action is known as positive modulation [17] and is considered to involve agents acting on allosteric sites on GABA_ARs remote from the orthosteric sites (GABA recognition sites). Allosteric sites are regarded as good targets for developing subtype-specific drugs since there is generally greater diversity between receptor subtypes in amino acid sequence at allosteric sites than at orthosteric sites [18, 19].

The importance of drug interactions with receptor subtypes has been highlighted by several recent findings involving genetically modified mice and ligands that show some selectivity for particular receptor subtypes. The finding is that different pharmacological actions of BDZ result from interactions with different GABA_ARs subtypes [20]. Sedation and anticonvulsive effects are mainly caused by BDZ binding to the $\alpha 1$ subtype, while anxiolytic effects were shown for the modulation of $\alpha 2$ -containing and very recently for the $\alpha 5$ -containing GABA_ARs. Muscle relaxation results from binding to the $\alpha 2$ - and $\alpha 3$ GABA_ARs subtypes, and motor coordination is impaired by modulation of $\alpha 1$ or $\alpha 3$ subtypes. The $\alpha 5$ subunit is furthermore involved in learning and memory. Finally, the recently discovered antihyperalgesic effect of benzodiazepines depends mainly on $\alpha 2$ -containing GABA_ARs in the spinal cord [21, 22].

Our knowledge of the certain subtype selective BDZ pharmacology revived the drug research towards GABA_ARs modulators. Selectivity is achieved by subtype-dependent binding affinity or efficacy. The latter results from full or partial agonism at one subtype but full or partial antagonism and weaker agonism (or negative agonism) at other subtypes. Among the most advanced fields is the search for non-sedative anxiolytic drugs, targeting the subunit $\alpha 2$ while sparing the $\alpha 1$ -subtype mediated effects, including sedation, motor coordination impairment, attention and memory deficits, and promotion of abuse [23]. Respective ligands are currently evaluated in biological and preclinical research. Subtype-selectivity of GABA_ARs modulators is of further interest towards the pharmacological intervention in pain [24]. Subtype-selective compounds targeting the $\alpha 2$ and/or $\alpha 3$ subunit of the GABA_ARs produce antihyperalgesia in mice and rats without sedation and tolerance induction [25]. These findings open new perspectives for more selective targeting of pain pathways with GABAergic drugs. BDZ produce antihyperalgesia in animal models by acting as agonists at the benzodiazepine-binding site of GABA_ARs. These compounds can therefore be studied to explore the potential usefulness of GABA-agonism in human pain conditions. Little is known about the effects of GABA_ARs targeting drugs on nociceptive processes in humans.

The initial strategy was based on identifying compounds with higher affinity for the 2 and -3 compared to the -1 and -5 subtypes. When this approach proved unsuccessful, the strategy was switched to developing compounds with subtype-selective efficacy [23]; that is, compounds which bind to all four subtypes but preferentially activate only 2- and 3- compared to 1- and 5- containing receptors (in other words, compounds with higher efficacy at 2 and 3 relative to 1 and 5 subtypes).

Propoxazepam is considered a promising agent and is undergoing clinical studies in Ukraine. Similar to gabapentinoid drugs, which are used in general medical practice in the treatment of neuropathic pain [26], propoxazepam also has an anticonvulsant effect [5, 9, 10], which explains the analgesic component in the pharmacological spectrum of the compound. Our data [5, 6, 9, 10] suggest that the mechanism of propoxazepam analgesic and anticonvulsant properties includes GABAergic and glycinergic systems. In the present study, the preferred isoforms of GABA_A-Rs in the pharmacological action of propoxazepam were determined.

The present studies have shown that the α subunit plays a significant role in determining the receptor's affinity for propoxazepam and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam (**Table 1, 2**). The rank order of decreasing EC₅₀ are $\alpha 1 = \alpha 5 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 3 > \alpha 4$ (propoxazepam) and $\alpha 1 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 3 > \alpha 4$ (3-hydroxypropoxazepam), and for E_{max} $\alpha 3 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 1 > \alpha 4$ (propoxazepam), $\alpha 3 > \alpha 1 > \alpha 2 > \alpha 5 > \alpha 4$ (3-hydroxypropoxazepam).

The integral characteristic of affinity can be the ratio E_{max}/EC₅₀ [27]. This value is convenient for comparing the effects of different compounds, for which the binding values (EC₅₀) and the values of the maximum induced effect (E_{max}) differ. As can be seen from the transformed data (**Table 3**), all the studied compounds have a lower affinity than diazepam for receptors containing the $\alpha 5$ subunit. However, propoxazepam exhibits tenfold (compared to diazepam) activity (taking into account the magnitude of the maximum effect) to the $\alpha 3$ subunit, which distinguishes it from 3-hydroxypropoxazepam. It should be noted that, based on the transformed data, propoxazepam also exhibits the highest activity among the studied compounds concerning receptors containing the $\alpha 2$ subunit, which, like the $\alpha 3$ subunit, is involved in the implementation of the analgesic effect.

The results obtained (**Table 1–3**) indicate that propoxazepam causes the maximum effect only on receptors containing $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ subunits, exceeding those on receptors containing other subunits. For 3-hydroxyphenazepam, high affinities (low EC_{50} values) are combined with significant maximum effect values at receptors containing $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ subunits. Considering that hypnotic, anticonvulsant, muscle relaxant and sedative actions are leading to 3-hydroxyphenazepam [28] in the pharmacological spectrum, this is consistent with the data obtained on receptor binding. For 3-hydroxypropoxazepam, there is no mention of a pronounced analgesic (antihyperalgesic) effect, the development of which is supposed to be mediated through the $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ subunits. Taking into account its high affinity for $\alpha 1$ -containing receptors, as well as close values of EC_{50} with $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$, it can be assumed that its action is not very specific in this regard and the effects caused mask a possible analgesic effect.

The molecular mechanisms of the interaction of BDZ with the α subunits of the $GABA_A$ receptor have been studied quite intensively using site-directed mutagenesis at the active sites of the subunit [29]. It was found that the degree of binding to the $\alpha 1$, and $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, and $\alpha 5$ subunits are due to a large extent to the presence of a histidine residue on the N- end of the extracellular region of these subunits. Instead, the $\alpha 4$ and $\alpha 6$ subunits contain an arginine residue and show no affinity for most classic BDZs. At the same time, the antagonist flumazenil, as well as bretazenil and Ro15-4513, with a common imidazobenzodiazepine structure, also show a high affinity for these subunits. In light of this fact, the previously existing opinion that the strength and severity of the effects of BDZ depend directly on their lipophilicity finds another explanation. Of course, lipophilicity makes a significant contribution to the rate of diffusion of molecules through biomembranes and their accumulation in the brain; however, the histidine fragment is more hydrophobic (-3.2 on the hydrophobicity scale [30]) than arginine (-4.5), which, respectively, increases the degree and probability of binding of more lipophilic 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives to these sites. Most BDZs used in clinical practice do not contain an electrophilic substituent at position 3, except for lorazepam, nozepam, oxazepam and temazepam. All of them and 3-hydroxypropoxazepam are distinguished by the presence of a hydroxyl group in position 3, which, apparently, facilitates binding to the histidine residue but reduces the selectivity for different subunits. In contrast, propoxazepam, having an alkoxy group (propyloxy), is capable of binding due to the oxygen of the ether group, and the presence of the propyl radical probably causes spatial (steric) obstacles, limiting the possibility of binding only to the $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ receptor subtypes.

Limitations of the study. The difference in binding to certain subtypes of GABA receptors is determined at intro conditions only. It does not involve the receptor's expression rate in specific regions and structures of the brain. Therefore, the understanding of the final physiological effects of benzodiazepines can be obtained only when considering relationships between receptors' subtype selectivity and their localization in brain structures.

Prospects for further research. Subunit-dependent selective affinity and maximum effect magnitude of different benzodiazepines have to be determined for proper relationships of structure-activity to be made.

5. Conclusions

Comprehensive knowledge about physiological and pharmacological functions of $GABA_A$ Rs subtypes defined by their α subunits has renewed the interest in that receptor system as a target for developing drugs with fewer side-effects than classical BDZ and the development of drugs with analgesics, cognition-enhancing and non-sedative properties). Many compounds have now been developed that display $GABA_A$ Rs subtype selectivity, either by affinity or efficacy. This may be primarily achieved with higher affinity only at the desired receptor subtype. Propoxazepam is a potent ligand of the $GABA_A$ Rs allosteric BDZ site, which exhibits functional selectivity for receptors containing $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, or $\alpha 5$ over those containing $\alpha 1$. Therefore, propoxazepam has the potential to provide analgesia with less sedation than non-selective BDZ.

However, it is not only the nature of the protein subunits that influence the diversity of function of $GABA_A$ Rs subtypes *in vivo*. Significant contributors to this diversity are presynaptic factors, including release probability and a number of release sites; factors that determine synaptic

GABA transients in the cleft, including diffusion and the actions of GABA transporters; and post-synaptic factors, including GABA_ARs subtypes, their location and number, their modulation by endogenous and exogenous factors, and their interactions with postsynaptic-anchoring proteins. In addition, the phosphorylation state of the subunits is very important with GABA_ARs, as with many other ligand-gated ion channels.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Funding

This work is part of the project financially supported by SLC “INTERCHEM”.

References

- [1] Ghit, A., Assal, D., Al-Shami, A. S., Hussein, D. E. E. (2021). GABAA receptors: structure, function, pharmacology, and related disorders. *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 19 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00224-0>
- [2] Zhu, S., Sridhar, A., Teng, J., Howard, R. J., Lindahl, E., Hibbs, R. E. (2022). Structural and dynamic mechanisms of GABAA receptor modulators with opposing activities. *Nature Communications*, 13 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32212-4>
- [3] Sigel, E., P. Luscher, B. (2011). A Closer Look at the High Affinity Benzodiazepine Binding Site on GABAA Receptors. *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry*, 11 (2), 241–246. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/156802611794863562>
- [4] Ralvenius, W. T., Benke, D., Acuña, M. A., Rudolph, U., Zeilhofer, H. U. (2015). Analgesia and unwanted benzodiazepine effects in point-mutated mice expressing only one benzodiazepine-sensitive GABAA receptor subtype. *Nature Communications*, 6 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms7803>
- [5] Golovenko, N. Ya., Larionov, V. B., Reder, A. S., Valivodz', I. P. (2017). An effector analysis of the interaction of propoxazepam with antagonists of GABA and glycine receptors. *Neurochemical Journal*, 11 (4), 302–308. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1819712417040043>
- [6] Golovenko, N. Ya., Voloshchuk, N. I., Andronati, S. A., Taran, I. V., Reder, A. S., Pashynska, O. S., Larionov, V. B. (2018). Antinociception induced by a novel benzodiazepine receptor agonist and bradykinin receptor antagonist in rodent acute and chronic pain models. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 5 (12), 79–88.
- [7] Golovenko, N. Ya., Kabanova, T. A., Andronati, S. A., Halimova, O. I., Larionov, V. B., Reder, A. S. (2020). Anti-inflammatory effects of propoxazepam on different models of inflammation. *International Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*, 5 (2), 105–112. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11603/ijmmr.2413-6077.2019.2.10900>
- [8] Voloshchuk, N. I., Reder, A. S., Golovenko, M. Y., Taran, I. V., Pashynska, O. S. (2017) Pharmacological analysis of neurochemical antinociceptive mechanisms of propoxazepam action. *Pharmacology and Drug Toxicology*, 1, 3–11.
- [9] Glovenko, M., Reder, A., Andronati, S., Larionov, V. (2019). Evidence for the involvement of the GABA-ergic pathway in the anticonvulsant and antinociception activity of Propoxazepam in mice and rats. *Journal of Pre-Clinical and Clinical Research*, 13 (3), 99–105. doi: <https://doi.org/10.26444/jpcpr/110430>
- [10] Golovenko, M. Ya., Larionov, V. B., Reder, A. S., Andronati, S. A., Valivodz', I. P., Yurpalova, T. O. (2018). Pharmacodynamics of Interaction between Propoxazepam and a GABA-Benzodiazepine Receptor-Ionophore Complex. *Neurophysiology*, 50 (1), 2–10. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11062-018-9711-9>
- [11] Andronati, S., Semenishyna, E., Pavlovsky, V., Simonov, Y., Makan, S., Boyko, I. et al. (2010). Synthesis, structure and affinity of novel 3-alkoxy-1,2-dihydro-3H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-ones for CNS central and peripheral benzodiazepine receptors. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45 (4), 1346–1351. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.12.027>
- [12] Sakimoto, Y., Oo, P. M.-T., Goshima, M., Kanehisa, I., Tsukada, Y., Mitsushima, D. (2021). Significance of GABAA Receptor for Cognitive Function and Hippocampal Pathology. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22 (22), 12456. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms222212456>
- [13] Zhang, Z., Tang, W. (2018). Drug metabolism in drug discovery and development. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*, 8 (5), 721–732. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2018.04.003>
- [14] Golovenko, M. Ya., Reder, A. S., Larionov, V. B., Andronati, S. A. (2022) Metabolic profile and mechanisms of gaba-targeted receptor propoxazepam metabolization in human hepatocytes. *Biotechnologia Acta*, 15 (1), 43–51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15407/biotech15.01.043>

- [15] Kemp, J. A., Marshall, G. R., Wong, E. H. F., Woodruff, G. N. (1987). The affinities, potencies and efficacies of some benzodiazepine-receptor agonists, antagonists and inverse-agonists at rat hippocampal GABAA-receptors. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 91 (3), 601–608. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.1987.tb11253.x>
- [16] Larionov, V. B., Golovenko, M. Ya., Reder, A. S. (2018). Propoxazepam conformation and its orientation in the GABAA-receptor binding site. *Ukrainian biopharmaceutical journal*, 1 (54), 10–17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24959/ubphj.18.150>
- [17] Allen, M. J., Sabir, S., Sharma, S. (2022). GABA Receptor. StatPearls Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526124/>
- [18] Ain, Q. U., Owen, R. M., Omoto, K., Torella, R., Bulusu, K. C., Pryde, D. C. et al. (2016). Analysis of Differential Efficacy and Affinity of GABAA ($\alpha 1/\alpha 2$) Selective Modulators. *Molecular Pharmaceutics*, 13 (11), 4001–4012. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.6b00813>
- [19] Jembrek, M., Vlainic, J. (2015). GABA Receptors: Pharmacological Potential and Pitfalls. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 21(34), 4943–4959. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612821666150914121624>
- [20] Chen, X., van Gerven, J., Cohen, A., Jacobs, G. (2018). Human pharmacology of positive GABA-A subtype-selective receptor modulators for the treatment of anxiety. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, 40 (5), 571–582. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41401-018-0185-5>
- [21] Rudolph, U., Möhler, H. (2014). GABAA Receptor Subtypes: Therapeutic Potential in Down Syndrome, Affective Disorders, Schizophrenia, and Autism. *Annual Review of Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 54 (1), 483–507. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-011613-135947>
- [22] Ralvenius, W. T., Acuña, M. A., Benke, D., Matthey, A., Daali, Y., Rudolph, U. et al. (2016). The clobazam metabolite N-desmethyl clobazam is an $\alpha 2$ preferring benzodiazepine with an improved therapeutic window for antihyperalgesia. *Neuropharmacology*, 109, 366–375. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2016.07.004>
- [23] Castellano, D., Shepard, R. D., Lu, W. (2021). Looking for Novelty in an “Old” Receptor: Recent Advances Toward Our Understanding of GABAARs and Their Implications in Receptor Pharmacology. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2020.616298>
- [24] Zeilhofer, H. U., Neumann, E., Munro, G. (2019). Spinal GABAA receptors for pain control: back to the future? *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 123 (2), e176–e179. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2019.01.030>
- [25] Knabl, J., Witschi, R., Hösl, K., Reinold, H., Zeilhofer, U. B., Ahmadi, S. et al. (2008). Reversal of pathological pain through specific spinal GABAA receptor subtypes. *Nature*, 451 (7176), 330–334. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06493>
- [26] Chincholkar, M. (2020) Gabapentinoids: pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics and considerations for clinical practice. *British Journal of Pain*, 14 (2), 104–114. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2049463720912496>
- [27] Ehlert, F. J., Griffin, M. T., Sawyer, G. W., Bailon, R. (1999). A simple method for estimation of agonist activity at receptor subtypes: comparison of native and cloned M3 muscarinic receptors in guinea pig ileum and transfected cells. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 289 (2), 981–992.
- [28] Voronina, T. A., Larionov, V. B., Golovenko, N. Y., Nerobkova, L. N., Gaidukov, I. O. (2014) Role of the 3-oximetabolite phenazepam and levan in realize their neurotropic efficacy. *Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics*, 1, 43–49.
- [29] Kelly, M. D., Smith, A., Banks, G., Wingrove, P., Whiting, P. W., Atack, J. et al. (2002). Role of the histidine residue at position 105 in the human $\alpha 5$ containing GABA receptor on the affinity and efficacy of benzodiazepine site ligands. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 135 (1), 248–256. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bjp.0704459>
- [30] Kyte, J., Doolittle, R. F. (1982). A simple method for displaying the hydropathic character of a protein. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 157 (1), 105–132. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2836\(82\)90515-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2836(82)90515-0)

Received date 11.08.2022

Accepted date 15.09.2022

Published date 30.09.2022

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article
under the Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: Reder, A., Larionov, V., Golovenko, M. (2022). Subunit-dependent interaction of propoxazepam and its metabolite with the γ -aminobutyric acid type a receptor. *EUREKA: Health Sciences*, 5, 10–18. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5679.2022.002649>